

Successful Awake Endotracheal Intubation in a Patient With Predicted Anatomical and Physiological Difficult Airway Undergoing Emergency Surgery at a Secondary-Level Hospital: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

The management of a predicted difficult airway represents a significant clinical challenge, particularly in emergency settings and in patients with associated anatomical and physiological alterations. Awake tracheal intubation has demonstrated high success rates and a favorable safety profile; however, its use remains limited.

We present the case of a 50-year-old female patient with late-onset sepsis secondary to chronic pyelonephritis who required an urgent left nephrectomy. During the preanesthetic assessment, multiple anatomical and physiopathological predictors of high complexity were identified, allowing classification as a predicted difficult airway with a mixed component. Given this scenario, awake endotracheal intubation was chosen, maintaining spontaneous ventilation, using airway topicalization, titrated sedoanalgesia with fentanyl and propofol, and videolaryngoscopy. Intubation was successful and without respiratory complications.

The coexistence of multiple anatomical and physiological predictors of difficult airway in the context of emergency surgery constitutes a high-risk scenario during anesthetic induction, with an increased likelihood of hypoxia and hemodynamic instability. In this context, awake tracheal intubation allows preservation of spontaneous ventilation and reduces the risk of airway management failure. The use of videolaryngoscopy, combined with adequate topical anesthesia and titrated sedation, facilitated a safe approach tailored to the operator’s experience and available resources.

Difficult airway management in emergency settings requires individualized decision-making based on comprehensive patient assessment, anesthesiologist experience, and the clinical environment. Awake tracheal intubation may contribute to optimizing perioperative safety, as demonstrated in the present case.

KEYWORDS: Difficult airway; Awake intubation; Videolaryngoscopy; Emergency surgery; Physiologically difficult airway.

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INTRODUCTION

The approach to a predicted difficult airway represents a significant challenge in critical scenarios and requires adequate training, anticipation, and planning. Awake tracheal intubation has demonstrated high success rates and a

favorable safety profile; however, its application in the anticipated management of the difficult airway remains limited. This may be related to the physical, mental, and psychological stress involved for the operator when

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performing the technique, both in elective and emergency surgeries (2,3,7).

The American Society of Anesthesiologists defines a difficult airway as a clinical situation in which a trained operator experiences difficulty with mask ventilation, supraglottic airway ventilation, or tracheal intubation. According to the Spanish Society of Anesthesiology, Resuscitation and Pain Therapy (SEDAR), this difficulty may manifest during face mask ventilation, use of supraglottic devices, or tracheal intubation (1).

Anatomical difficult airway refers to patients in whom anatomical alterations that may hinder ventilation or tracheal intubation are identified through various tests, classifications, or physical characteristics. These include the Mallampati classification, Patil–Aldrete index, sternomental distance, interincisor distance, mandibular protrusion, Bellhouse–Doré classification, predictive index of difficult intubation, short or thick neck, obesity, presence of masses or tumors displacing the airway, beard, or facial fractures. More recently, the concept of the physiologically difficult airway has been described, occurring in critically ill adult patients with physiopathological alterations such as hypoxemia, hypotension, severe metabolic acidosis, and heart failure, conditions that increase risk during airway management (1,2,3,4).

Despite advances, airway-related complications remain a significant cause of cardiorespiratory arrest, with major adverse events including death, brain injury, cardiac arrest, and trauma. In secondary-level hospitals, where human and technological resources may be limited, the chosen strategy becomes particularly relevant and reinforces the value of sharing clinical experiences in such settings (1,2,3,7).

The Difficult Airway Society (DAS) proposes a stepwise approach to airway management, beginning with tracheal intubation, followed by supraglottic airway devices, face mask ventilation, and finally emergency airway access. In cases of predicted difficult airway, awake endotracheal intubation has demonstrated high success rates and a wide safety margin, as it preserves spontaneous ventilation and airway tone, thereby reducing the risk of complications associated with anesthetic induction (2,7).

CLINICAL CASE

We present the case of a 50-year-old female patient diagnosed with late-onset sepsis secondary to chronic left pyelonephritis, for whom urgent surgical intervention for left nephrectomy was requested.

Relevant medical history included type 2 diabetes mellitus and systemic arterial hypertension of eight years' duration, with poor adherence to unspecified treatment, recurrent

refractory chronic pyelonephritis, and a four-year history of an unstudied anterior cervical mass at the level of the thyroid cartilage.

The patient presented to the emergency department with severe bilateral lumbar pain and unquantified fever. She reported a three-month history of urinary tract symptoms, during which she received multiple pharmacological regimens without clinical improvement. Paraclinical studies were performed, including renal ultrasound showing chronic changes consistent with pyelonephritis. At admission, diagnoses of diabetic ketoacidosis and acute exacerbation of chronic pyelonephritis were established.

During the following ten days of hospitalization, comprehensive medical treatment was provided, resulting in resolution of diabetic ketoacidosis. However, the urinary infectious focus showed antibiotic resistance, progressing to clinical features consistent with sepsis and late septic physiopathological changes, including moderate normocytic normochromic anemia, thrombocytosis, coagulation abnormalities, hydroelectrolytic and acid–base disturbances, mild hyponatremia, mild hyperkalemia, and mild hyperphosphatemia.

Once the emergency procedure was indicated, preanesthetic assessment revealed a neurologically intact patient with spontaneous ventilation, oxygen saturation of 99% on room air, tachycardia without hypotension, and no vasopressor support. She was fasting. Weight was 80 kg and height 1.60 m.

Airway evaluation revealed multiple predictors of difficult ventilation and intubation, including Mallampati IV, oral opening grade II, sternomental distance grade III, Patil–Aldrete grade III, mandibular protrusion grade II, short cylindrical neck with limited cervical extension (Bellhouse–Doré II), and a fixed anterior cervical mass measuring approximately 3 × 2 cm at the level of the thyroid cartilage. Based on these findings, the airway was classified as a predicted difficult airway, scoring 15 out of 18 points on the predictive index of difficult intubation.

Laboratory findings included hemoglobin 9.7 g/dL, hematocrit 30.3%, platelets $488 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, prothrombin time 19.5 seconds with 47% activity, INR 1.76, activated partial thromboplastin time 28.8 seconds, sodium 132 mmol/L, potassium 5 mmol/L, phosphate 2.6 mmol/L, and leukocytes $8.5 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ with 67% neutrophils and 23.7% lymphocytes.

Given the anatomical and physiological characteristics, awake tracheal intubation with mild sedation was planned. Videolaryngoscopy with hyperangulated and Macintosh blades was prepared according to need, along with readiness for emergency surgical airway access (Figure 1).

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Figure 1. Anatomical features

SOURCE. Photograph taken for the clinical record and academic purposes.

The anesthetic plan, risks, and possible complications were explained to the patient, who provided informed consent. The patient received tranexamic acid 1 g intravenously in the preoperative area. Upon arrival in the operating room, standard noninvasive monitoring was initiated, with baseline vital signs within normal limits. Preoxygenation was performed using a face mask with 100% inspired oxygen. Airway topical anesthesia was administered using lidocaine spray (200 mg orally), along with sedation using fentanyl 150 µg intravenously and manual propofol infusion targeting a plasma concentration of 1 µg/kg/min.

After adequate analgesia was achieved, oxygen delivery was switched from face mask to nasal cannula at 5 L/min. Diagnostic videolaryngoscopy using a hyperangulated blade revealed a POGO score of 0% with good tolerance; therefore, a second videolaryngoscopy using a Macintosh size 3 blade was performed, improving glottic visualization to a POGO score of 25% and allowing successful placement of a 7.5 mm Murphy orotracheal tube with the aid of a stylet, classified as M-25-D. Oxygen saturation remained at 99% throughout the procedure (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Visualization of the vocal cords by videolaryngoscopy.

SOURCE. Photograph taken for the clinical record and academic purposes

Correct tube placement was confirmed by videolaryngoscopic visualization, bilateral auscultation, visualization of air column, capnography waveform, and capnometry. Anesthetic induction was then completed with cisatracurium 10 mg, and anesthesia was maintained with sevoflurane under volume-controlled mechanical ventilation. During the intraoperative period, the patient remained initially stable under general anesthesia and mechanical ventilation. Surgical bleeding from the renal hilum amounted to 750 mL, resulting in refractory hypotension despite crystalloid resuscitation. Blood products were transfused, and vasopressor support with norepinephrine was initiated, achieving adequate hemodynamic response with mean arterial pressure maintained above 65 mmHg. At the end of the procedure, the patient emerged from anesthesia through metabolic clearance. Once protective airway reflexes, adequate spontaneous ventilation, and a RASS score of -2 were present, extubation was performed without complications.

The patient was transferred to the post-anesthesia care unit neurologically intact, breathing spontaneously with supplemental oxygen via nasal cannula, and hemodynamically stable without vasopressor support.

DISCUSSION

Airway management in emergency surgery is associated with a higher incidence of difficulty and complications compared with elective procedures. In the present case, the coexistence of multiple anatomical and physiological predictors of difficult airway created a high-risk clinical scenario, primarily due to the potential for hypoxia and hemodynamic instability during anesthetic induction. This risk was further increased by the possibility of a “cannot ventilate, cannot intubate” scenario or failed emergency airway access, conditioned by the patient’s anatomical features (2,3). In such scenarios, individualized risk-benefit analysis is essential to determine the most appropriate airway management strategy (1).

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According to the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA), awake tracheal intubation has reported success rates between 88% and 100%, supporting its safety profile in patients with predicted difficult airway. Unlike conventional anesthetic induction, this strategy preserves spontaneous ventilation and airway tone until tracheal access is secured, reducing the risk of hypoxia, particularly in patients with low apnea tolerance, and avoiding complications related to unexpected loss of airway (1,2,7).

The British Journal of Anaesthesia (2025) recommendations propose videolaryngoscopy as Plan A in difficult airway management. Concordantly, Jiménez-Contreras et al. report the usefulness of videolaryngoscopy in difficult airway scenarios, particularly when flexible fiberoptic bronchoscopy is unavailable or operator experience is limited, given its prolonged learning curve. In these contexts, videolaryngoscopy is described as an effective and safe alternative for awake tracheal intubation, with high first-attempt success rates (7,12).

Regarding blade type, Köhl et al. conducted a randomized controlled trial highlighting hyperangulated blades, associating them with higher first-attempt success rates, shorter intubation times, and improved glottic visualization. However, in the present case, limited experience with hyperangulated blades prompted a strategy change to a Macintosh blade, improving glottic visualization and enabling successful intubation. This finding underscores the importance of adapting technique and device choice to operator experience rather than strictly adhering to general recommendations (8).

Airway topicalization is the cornerstone of successful awake tracheal intubation. Lidocaine is the most commonly used local anesthetic due to its favorable safety profile and low risk of systemic toxicity when used within recommended limits. Its absorption depends on the route and method of administration, and a maximum dose of 9 mg/kg is generally recommended. In this case, 200 mg of lidocaine was administered via atomization with satisfactory results (7).

Although adequate topicalization does not necessarily require sedation, minimal titrated sedation may be used to improve patient comfort and reduce anxiety, provided oversedation is avoided. Guidelines suggest drugs with predictable and reversible pharmacological profiles, such as remifentanyl, dexmedetomidine, or benzodiazepines. However, due to lack of availability of recommended agents, low-dose propofol infusion was used in this case. Although its use in awake intubation is not widely described, its rapid onset, ease of titration, and short metabolism allowed maintenance of superficial sedation without compromising spontaneous ventilation or oxygenation. Nonetheless, its use should be individualized and strictly monitored due to the risk of respiratory depression (7,13).

CONCLUSIONS

Difficult airway management in emergency settings requires individualized decision-making aimed at minimizing risk and ensuring patient safety. In this context, anesthetic strategy selection should not rely solely on algorithms or specific devices but rather on a comprehensive assessment that considers the patient's clinical condition, informed consent, anesthesiologist experience, and available resources. This approach allows adaptation of existing recommendations to complex clinical situations and optimization of perioperative outcomes. Despite its wide safety margin and high success rates, awake tracheal intubation remains underutilized; as demonstrated in this case, its use may significantly enhance perioperative safety.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Case information was handled confidentially and anonymized, ensuring protection of personal data. This study was reviewed and approved by the Research Committee (CI-2025-053-HGC) and the Research Ethics Committee (CEI-2025-053-HGC) of the General Hospital of Cancún.

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